

HOW CONSUMER REVIEWS INFLUENCE THE PERCEIVED TRUSTWORTHINESS OF PURCHASING AN ONLINE PRODUCT

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ABSTRACT

Online client reviews have come increasingly important to the business world currently as further and further druggies make use of social media platforms to look for product information. For the tourism assiduity this problem is especially current due to the fact that its products and services are high threat and intangible. thus, it's pivotal to understand how exactly online client reviews impact guests and what aspects of an online client review are influential when it comes to its perceived responsibility. The part of the critic's profile has not been delved considerably so far and may play a part in the perceived responsibility of a review. The present study, which has been conducted as an online check, aims at chancing out further about the problem by assessing particular opinions and presenting different reviews to the actors. The results show that the repliers' general station towards online client reviews is positive and that they generally find them honest and believable. Gender and age don't feel to have an effect on the perception. still, the profile of the critic does feel to impact the perceived responsibility in a direct relationship. Counteraccusations of these results are that marketers may be suitable to identify which reviews are most likely to impact their business and why. They may prioritize which client reviews to reply to in order to reduce the negative effect of particular reviews

Keywords

Responsibility, Client, Marketers, Reviews.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Relevance of topic

The business world has changed greatly over the once many times, substantially due to the rising significance and wide use of social media, or web2.0 (Forbes, 2013). The largely interactive web2.0 world gives further power to the consumer which are now suitable to mandate the nature of the marketing content presented on the internet. Social networks and blogs 'enable individualities to produce, partake, and recommend information'(Hannah et al., 2011), 'estimate products, make recommendations to connections or musketeers, and link current purchases to unborn purchases through status updates and twitter feeds '(Forbes, 2013), and have been honored for impacting the relinquishment and use of products and services(Lee, 2008). still, consumers don't only use the internet for probing the companies they want to buy from, but to engage with the companies as well as with other consumers who may have precious perceptivity into certain products and services (Hannah et al., 2011). A global study revealed that nearly two-thirds of repliers read online client reviews before making a purchase (Wei & Lu, 2013).

The so- called stoner- generated content generates a high quantum of electronic word- of- mouth, or eWOM, that influences the character of a company and its products (DiMauro & Bulmer, 2014). EWOM refers to all positive and negative statements made by consumers about the products or services of a company or the company itself (Lee, 2008; Karakaya & Barnes, 2012). In addition, the miracle has been associated with the ripple effect, which principally means that a putatively small and insignificant comment can have a far reaching and significant impact. thus, company websites are no longer the only source of information for consumers. The participated opinions and gests of socially-connected consumers are taken into consideration when gathering information about a product or service (DiMauro & Bulmer, 2014) and, next to that, these online opinions are perceived as inversely secure as the brand websites themselves (Lee, 2008). Consumers more frequently calculate on the recommendations and expert opinion of a friend or familiarity set up within their social media network (Forbes, 2013). Taking into consideration all these data, it becomes egregious that companies currently have lower control over the information available about them on the internet and that they're especially vulnerable to what consumers partake online. They don't control the dispersion of product information due to the large extent to which consumers use the new interactive arenas, similar as web2.0 (Wei & Lu, 2013).

From a consumer perspective, these developments are substantially positive. The global reach of the internet gives them the possibility to gather information and opinions of peers from each over the world and, therefore, define brands without the influence of companies (Pires et al., 2006), as they might present different or lacking information on

their own websites in order to produce a favorable image of their immolation in the guests' minds. According to DiMauro & Bulmer (2014), 37 of buyers find quality an essential factor and 27 consider information set up on social media networks as a importing factor. For that reason, it's intriguing to see how and to what extent these online client reviews impact consumers looking for information online.

1.2 Background

In order to more understand social media and its colorful functionalities, the honeycomb frame (Figure 1), developed by Kietzmann et al. (2011), will be taken into consideration. The model can be used as a lens for understanding social media using seven functional structure blocks. These are presence, sharing, connections, identity, exchanges, character and groups. When looking at the counteraccusations of each block, enterprises can decide how they should engage with social media. Kietzmann et al. (2012) describes three important ways in which enterprises should make use of the model. First, the social media stoner experience can be determined by determining the primary, secondary and tertiary structure blocks of a platform. Second, directors can use the model as an logical lens to figure out their community's requirements and choose an applicable social media platform consequently. Third, the honeycomb model can be used as a lens for covering the community's requirements and the social media tools the establishment accordingly needs to acclimatize. The seven structure blocks aren't mutually exclusive and don't all need to be included when it comes to a specific social media platform. Each block presents an important social media miracle that can be understood by applying colorful scientific propositions. 'Identity' describes the extent to which druggies choose to reveal their individualities on a social media platform in terms of particular information. 'Groups' stands for the openings druggies have to organize themselves into groups and distinct sub-communities within a social media platform. druggies themselves can form and join these groups according to their particular interests. The 'relationship' structure block deals with the extent to which druggies can be related to other druggies. Relate is defined as 'two or further consumers who have some form of relationship that leads them to discourse, share objects, meet up or simply just list each other as a friend or addict' (Kietzmann et al., 2012). 'Character' is about the socially shaped opinion of enterprises or individualities that's grounded on previous guests participated through word of mouth, content in the popular press and other sources. For that reason, it's important for enterprises to produce positive links to their products and brands. The coming structure block is 'presence'. It's about the extent to which druggies know whether other druggies are accessible, or online, at a specific time. 'exchanges' is about the extent to which druggies communicate with each other using the social media platform. The last block, 'participating', is about the extent to which druggies are suitable to change, distribute and admit contents.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study totally analyzes applicable scientific literature that's dealing with analogous issues as the one presented in this paper. Issues similar as social media, online client reviews, the tourism sector and TripAdvisor are thus being covered. These issues also serve as crucial words when searching for applicable literature. The hunt machines Google Scholar and Scopus have been used for gathering literature. After having set up a variety of papers, they've been checked for applicability to this study. That way, infelicitous papers have been excluded right way. Every epitome has been scrutinized according to the crucial words and the content in general as well as the time of publication as everything associated with web2.0, which is characterized by technological development, is dynamic and changing snappily over time and needs to be over- to- date. With the information collected from the literature, a literature review has been collected in order to get an overview of the rearmost and most important information regarding the content at hand. This also helps the anthology to come familiar with the content in an easy and effective manner.

Coming to the literature review, an online check has been conducted in order to be suitable to assess the issue with a applicable data set. This was especially important as this study is looking at TripAdvisor in particular and there's presently no data available specifically related to this content. The online check has been created and anatomized with the help of Google Tools. The distribution happed via several social media platforms, for illustration, Facebook and LinkedIn, and also viae-mail. The whole document can be set up in the excursus (see Appendix Section10.1). The questions posed in the online check have been constructed according to Babbie's (2013) guidelines for asking questions in checks. All particulars are moreover questions or statements that are unrestricted- ended. That way, the answers have lesser uniformity and are accordingly easier to reuse and dissect. Also, special attention has been paid to the answer orders and that they're total. In numerous cases repliers have the chance to fill in an own response in case their answer has not been handed to make sure that all options are covered. The online check has been made available for repliers for a period of 5 days and latterly the analysis has been conducted with the help of Google Tools, Microsoft Excel and SPSS. SPSS has substantially been used to assess possible connections between variables by rendering the data and also collecting cross tabulations and looking for correlations

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

3.1 Social Media, Online Customer Reviews & eWOM

An online client review is defined as 'a type of product information and evaluation created by druggies on the base of their own gests. The review information is posted on either the websites of the online stores or on third party

websites' (Wei & Lu, 2013). numerous websites, similar as Facebook, Twitter and Amazon, grease online client reviews of products, services and enterprises. druggies are suitable to write about and partake their particular gests on these platforms so that other consumers have the chance to read about first- hand gests and get information that has not been published by the companies themselves. Also, online client reviews, in comparison to traditional word- of- mouth, have several benefits. They're presto, savable and anonymous, and transcend time and space by being online (Wei & Lu, 2013; Litvin et al., 2005). That way, all online client reviews have a global reach and are readily available to everyone that wishes to read them. Eventually, online client are the most accessible and current form of eWOM (Yoo & Gretzel, 2008).

Park et al. (2007) point out three major differences between traditional word of mouth and online client reviews. The first difference is the influence of traditional word- of- mouth which is typically limited to a lower original network. On the negative to that, online client reviews have a far wider reach due to the fact that they're accessible to consumers each over the world. Secondly, merchandisers don't have any influence on traditional word- of- mouth. They can decide whether they would like to give consumers with the occasion to review their products on their website. nonetheless, a lot of reviews are posted on independent platforms currently, so that the degree to which merchandisers have influence over them is veritably limited. Thirdly, traditional word- of- mouth generally comes from people that are familiar to the consumer, similar as family or musketeers, whereas with online client reviews the information source is generally unknown.

Coming to that, online forums feel to have lesser credibility and are easier to relate to from a consumer perspective (Wei & Lu, 2013; Park et al., 2007). Source credibility has frequently been mentioned as a pivotal factor when it comes to the effectiveness of a communication. Naturally, it depends on the anthology's perception of the critic's responsibility and moxie (Karakaya & Barnes, 2012). The fact that the reviews have been written by fellow druggies evokes empathy and accordingly leads consumers to trust the information further than information published on the merchandisers' websites. Lee (2008) agrees with these findings and farther describes the online client reviews as more applicable to the druggies and mentions that the fact that other druggies have contributed them as the main reason for that. In that regard, Cheung et al. (2008) point out that social media platforms are generally being considered secure by druggies and that druggies also find online client reviews to be unprejudiced. The further reviews there are, the more likely consumers are to believe the recommendations and perceive the product in a positive light (Park et al., 2007).

As explained by Wei and Lu (2013), Park et al., online customer reviews as a form of electronic WOM have two roles. (2007) and Li et al. (2008). On the one hand, they get information about the product, and on the other hand, they get advice from the supervisor. Online customer reviews act as information providers, offering user opinions about products, including honest and fair advice on product quality and what's not good. These reviews are not typically found on company websites and can be especially helpful in users' purchasing decisions. Share your personal experiences and opinions as an expert, reviewer or reviewer to help other users make purchasing decisions. Together they make it easier for other users to determine the quality of the product.

Also Park et al. (2007) noted three differences between the information provided by sellers and the information provided by online consumers. These differences are based on the description of the two roles and should be understood when understanding the customer. The first difference is the reliability of the site, which often affects the level of trust. As noted above, previous research (e.g. Lee, 2008) has shown that online customer reviews are generally considered more trustworthy by consumers because they believe that other users will not hide what appears to be bad about the product or service. Honesty is a big issue in this case and sellers need to highlight the quality of the products on their websites. The second difference mentioned by Park et al. (2007) is the fact that online customer reviews appear to be more customer-focused. Reviews sometimes include usage, pros and cons based on the customer's perspective and experience, which is more relevant to the customer rather than the target, and product descriptions are often found on sales websites. The final difference is how the data object is displayed. Retail websites often have templates to display each item.

But online customer reviews are subjective and opinionated and may contain many or few words. However, when done well, reviews can still provide important and valuable information. However, more objective and literature reviews are more supportive than theoretical reviews (Park et al., 2007).

3.2 Online customer reviews in the Tourism Sector

Many researchers have concluded that the majority of consumers find information by reading customer reviews online before making a purchasing decision (Cheung et al., 2008; Forbes, 2013; Lee et al.), (2008) and with the emergence of Internet technology, more and more travelers are searching for information online texts (Litvin et al., 2005). In this sense, finding travel-related information is one of the most popular online activities (Yoo and Gretzel, 2008). In the travel industry, which is characterized by high-risk purchases, it is common for customers to consult customers online. Products carry high risk because they are not harmful and cannot be evaluated before actual use (Litvin et al., 2005 ; Del Chiappa, 2011). Therefore, electronic WOM is particularly important where consumers are constantly seeking reviews from online user groups to reduce uncertainty. What is called Internet 2.0 or Tourism 2.0 in Tourism includes bookmarks, online forums, customer rating and review systems, blogs, photo and video sharing, etc. includes (Del

Chiappa, 2011). Del Chiappa (2011) added that these information have more credibility among consumers than traditional travel information because they share their experiences personally.

Some researchers have found that online customer reviews have the biggest impact. The impact of tourism products relative to other tourism products (Del Chiappa, 2011; Yoo and Gretzel, 2008; Melian-Gonzalez et al., 2013). Online customer reviews are also considered the most important factor in choosing accommodation, while other variables such as location are also taken into account (Melian-Gonzalez et al., 2013).

Bronner and Hoog (2010) conducted a research study and obtained many important characteristics from the customer profile findings of online customer analysis in business tourism. These are as follows. First, these customers are generally under 55 years of age. Second, they come from high-income and lower-middle-income groups. Third, most of them are couples with or without children.

3.3 Conceptual Model

After reviewing the documents on the current topic and clearly seeing the relationship between the important items, the following voluntarily created model emerged (see Figure 2). This conceptual framework will help clarify the significance of the study and provide a framework for analysis.

2 Behavior on Social Media Platforms

All Participants stated that they use at least one social media platform regularly . Since this survey was published on social media platforms, it can be said that participants' participation in the survey is a prerequisite. Responses indicate that most participants use two or more social media sites (see Figure 5).

Social Media Platform Usage

The two most popular platforms among respondents are Facebook and YouTube, with 97.2% and 84% respectively. This is followed by LinkedIn (39.6%), Instagram (30.2%), Twitter (23.6%) and blogs (16%). Additionally, participants in this study rarely use Pinterest and Myspace.

In addition to the most used platforms, participants were also asked to estimate the time they spend on social media platforms per week. The highest figure given by a participant was 70 hours, meaning 10 hours a day were spent on social media platforms. Generally, this number is between 10 and 30 hours, with each participant working an average of 18.5 hours per week. This means on average it will take 2 to 3 hours Daily use of social media platforms.

Type of Platform used for reading Online Customer Reviews

The majority (i.e. 88.1%) said they use stores like Amazon for this purpose. Amazon, like many other websites, sells products and allows customers to review the products they have purchased. 73.3% use independent reviews and 49.5% use video platforms. Very few respondents (30.7%) read personal comments and 12.9% use other platforms not mentioned in the response section. For example, six respondents said they often find products on tweakers.net, an independent review site for technologies such as smartphones and laptops. More specifically, regarding the review site, approximately 71.3% use Amazon's user reviews. Others use TripAdvisor, Google My Business and other sites.

Participants were also asked to rate their level of agreement with different statements in online customer reviews. 24.8% of respondents agreed and 62.4% agreed with the statement "I think online customer reviews are very important when collecting product information." Only 2% disagreed with the statement and 10.9% neither agreed nor disagreed. It can therefore be concluded that for most of the survey respondents, online customer reviews play an important role in purchasing. Similar results were found for the statement "I often use customer reviews in the literature when choosing products." Next post "Online customer reviews influence my product choices." 12.9% agreed with all these statements and 63.4% agreed.

5.4 Travel Review Sites and TripAdvisor in particular

5.4.1 General Information about the respondents' perception of Travel Review Sites

As mentioned in the introduction, this article uses TripAdvisor as a case study to understand online consumers . Customer reviews. TripAdvisor is primarily used to collect information about business travel. Of the 106 people surveyed, 100 said they had traveled in the last 12 months. When asked how often they read online customer reviews before booking a holiday, 32.1% said "often", 36.8% said "often", 25.5% said "sometimes" and only 3.8% He chose the "No" option. Additionally, the majority of respondents (i.e. 68.9%) rated online customer reviews above 3 before booking a holiday, on a scale of 1 (not important) to 5 (very important). You can find these reviews on many websites. 61.3% of visitors visited tripadvisor.com, 54.7% visited booking.com, 44.3% visited other sites, and the smallest

shares were expedia.com and Hotels.com. .

Some statements in the survey relate to TripAdvisor and participants' general comments on the site. Participants were asked to rate on a 5-point scale from "disagree" to "agree." Regarding the statement "Find reliable online user reviews based on data on TripAdvisor", 9.4% of respondents said "agree", 49.1% said "agree", 21.7% said "disagree or disagree" and 6.6% "disagree" or "disagree". I completely disagree'. Almost the same results were found for the statement "The most reliable for me are online customer reviews on TripAdvisor." Participants were then asked to express their opinion on the statement "I often doubt the trustworthiness of online customers." Only 2.8% said "strongly agree", while 19.8% said "agree". 30.2% "neither agree nor disagree", 34.9% "disagree" and 2.8% "strongly disagree". These responses indicate that respondents' overall attitude towards TripAdvisor and customer reviews is extremely positive. Most people think they are trustworthy and reliable. Relatedly, most respondents also stated that they believe most online customer reviews are honest and trustworthy. More than 54.7% "agree" or "agree with the statement" and 22.6% "disagree or disagree". In the next part of the survey, the last statement, "It is important for me to know who wrote the review," looks interesting. 16% strongly agreed with the statement, 31.3% agreed and 29.2% neither agreed nor disagreed, meaning only 10.4% disagreed and 3.8% strongly disagreed.

5.4.2 TripAdvisor Reviews and how they are perceived by users

To better understand how customer reviews impact customer needs, we offer four ways to review TripAdvisor for our survey participants. Reviews can be positive or negative, long or short, and reviewers have many or few positive comments. Differences can be found in the Annex (see Section 10.1). All reviews were selected based on specific characteristics of interest to the researchers of this study. Review 1 is a medium-length, positive review where the reviewer has a good reputation in the TripAdvisor community. 2. The comment is long and rude and the commenter's profile is not verified. Description 3 is short and simple and includes a profile review. The last review, review #4, is of medium length and quality, and the reviewer profile has not yet been verified. The length of the review is marked as the word count of the review. Short stories of less than 50 words, medium-length stories of 50 to 100 words, and long stories of more than 100 words. Participants were asked about the reliability of the review, how long it lasted, whether it would affect their decision to choose the hotel, whether the review was written by a trusted person, whether it was well-written and objective. The results show significant differences between tests in terms of perceived reliability and other factors (see Exhibits 2-6).

5.4.2.1 Credibility of Reviews

The statement about the "above assessment" seems credible. The number of respondents who agreed and strongly agreed with the 1st statement

is more than the 2nd and 3rd statement, i.e. 80.2%, i.e. 34.1% and 50.9% respectively. Comment 4 received a score of 63.2%.

5.4.2.2 Lengths of Reviews

Reviews marked as "short" in this study have a high number of respondents who agree and strongly agree with the bar "The above review is of appropriate length". These are review #1 and review #4 with 78.3% and 69.8% respectively. In review #2, which has a long text, 42.5% disagree with the statement and 30.2% agree. For review #3, which is very short, the same figures are 34% and 19.8%.

5.4.2.3 Extent to which Review would influence Hotel Choice

The additional statement "The above review would influence my hotel selection decision" also shows a higher percentage of "agree" and "strongly agree" in review #1 (73.6%) and review #4 (46.2%) than in the other two. These numbers correlate with the percentages given in the first statement. Both reviews #1 and #4 score high on credibility and whether a review would influence respondents' decisions.

5.4.2.3 Trustworthiness of Reviewer

The fourth statement, "The above review was written by someone I trust," shows a variety of responses. Review #1 appears to be perceived by study respondents as a credible reviewer, with 68.9% either agreeing or strongly agreeing with the statement. However, review #2 has a high number of respondents who do not find the reviewer trustworthy. 57.5% either disagree or strongly disagree with the statement. Then review #3 has more split responses. 38.7% neither agree nor disagree and 41.5% agree. Approximately the same applies to review No. 4

5.4.2.4 The way the review is written

Finally, the statement "The review is well written and objective" produced mixed results for all four reviews. 63.2% of respondents agree or strongly agree that review #1 was well written and objective. Review #2 has more negative results with 26.4% strongly disagree and 46.2% disagree. A more diverse set of responses can be seen for review #3. 36.8% disagree that the review is well written and objective, while 23.6% neither agree nor disagree and 24.5% agree. In review #4, 40.6% of respondents neither agree nor disagree with the bar and 36.8% agree. 14.2% disagree. Possible explanations for these differences and relationships between variables will be further explored in the next section

4. DATA ANALYSIS

4.1 Relationships between the different variables

4.1.1 Age and Social Media Behavior

The first variable to analyze is age. This will be done in relation to the various results found in the online survey. In order to better understand the behavior of the respondents and the relationship to age, four different age groups were created in the analysis process. These are 15-20, 21-25, 26-30 and 31 and elderly. There are 16%, 67.9%, 10.4% and 5.7% of respondents in these groups.

First, we look at age in relation to the number of hours spent on social media platforms each week (see Appendix Table 7). This variable was also divided into four groups, namely 1-10 hours, 11-20, 21-30 and 30 or more. Age group 1 has the most people who spend 11-20 hours a week, 47.1%. The average person in this group spends 15 hours online. Most people in age group 2, which is 34.7%, spend 21-30 hours on social media platforms. The average person here spends about 20 hours on the Internet, which is already 5 hours more than a person in age group 1. In age group 3, 36.4% of respondents spend 11 to 20 hours online, which is the highest number in the age group. On average, a respondent from this group spends 18 hours on social media platforms. The last age group has the most respondents, 50%, spend 0 to 10 hours online, 11 hours on average. From these results, it can be said that the use of social media among the respondents increases after the age of 20, then slowly decreases after the age of 26 and then decreases more significantly at the age of 31. Thus, young adults are the group of respondents using social media platforms most often

4.1.2 Gender and Online Customer Reviews

When you look at the frequency of how often men and women check online customer reviews, you don't find any significant differences (see Appendix Table 8). 36% of women and 28.6% of men check reviews "very often" and the same figures for "often" are 40% and 33.9%. The only difference is that no women stated that they "never" check online customer reviews, and that there were 4 men who did.

Similar results can be found when looking at the importance respondents attach to online customer reviews (see Appendix Table 9). The rating ranges from 1 (lowest) to 5 (highest) and 26% of women ticked 5, while 16.1% of men did so. 46% of women checked 4 and 50% of men. 1 was chosen by only 2% of women and 5.4% of men.

Another interesting relationship to look at is the degree to which different genders think reviews are generally trustworthy and honest. Again, there are no noticeable differences between men and women of the current group of respondents (see Appendix Table 10). 4% of women and 3.6% of men completely agree with the statement, and 56% of women and 46.4% of men agree with the statement. Only 8% of women and 14.3% of men disagree, and less than 4% strongly disagree for both sexes.

When asked whether it is important to know who wrote the review, the gender % of women and again do not show large differences (see Appendix Table 11). 18% of females and 14.3% of males strongly agree with this bar, in addition, 32% of females and 30.4% of males agree with it. Only 14% of women and 7.1% of men disagree with the statement. The same figures for those who strongly disagree are 4% and 3.6%

6.2 TripAdvisor

Influencing factors on perceived credibility Factors affecting trust To understand whether anything affects the perceived trustworthiness of reviews, different relationships need to be taken into account. Using Pearson correlation (2-tailed) (ranging from -1 to +1), it will be examined whether review length (short, medium, or long) has an impact on perceived trustworthiness in the full review. For the purpose of this study, trust is considered to be related to trust here. As stated in the literature review, trust is often related to the level of trust (Park et al., 2007). The relative efficiency of feedback 1 is 0.41, feedback 1. 0.162/2, comment 3.0, 355, comment no. 4 becomes 0.334. As a rule, all relationships except comments are significant 2. Therefore, it is questionable how long the effect on perceived reliability will last.

Now, it will be examined whether there is a relationship between the statement "the above review was written by someone I consider reliable" and "the above review appears to be reliable". Again, all analyzes using Pearson correlation (2-tailed) showed a positive relationship between the two variables. The correlation coefficient of review #1 is 0.631, the correlation coefficient of review #2 is 0.566, and the correlation coefficient of review #1 is 0.566. 3 a

0.521 and review no. 4 0.596. Since the correlation coefficient is positive, it can be concluded that the more trustworthy the reviewer appears, the more trustworthy the reader is in viewing the review as a whole.

At the beginning of the survey, participants were also asked to indicate whether they believed in the trustworthiness of online consumers. However, this particular perspective did not appear to influence how participants evaluated the four assessments presented to them. All four correlation coefficients are close to 0, i.e. between -0.1 and 0.1. Therefore there is no relationship. Other variables such as age or ethnicity also had no significant impact on reliability.

6.2.1 Influencing factors on perceived trustworthiness of reviewer

For each review, participants were asked to indicate whether the review was well written and well-intentioned. Looking at the reliability statements of the author's review, positive and significant correlations were found in all four reviews. The corresponding coefficients are 0.701, 0.506, 0.661, and 0.419, respectively. These results suggest that when a user perceives a review as well-written and objective, they are more likely to view the reviewer as trustworthy

5. DISCUSSION & CONCLUSION

5.1 Influencing factors on the perceived Trustworthiness of Online Customer Reviews

The introduction of the article includes research questions and three sub-questions. The main research question is "How much do variables influence the perceived trustworthiness of online reviews?" Answers will be given based on research with the help of three questions.

The first question is "What do customers think about online customer reviews?" Looking at the results, it can be seen that almost all of the participants in this research used various customer reviews before purchasing. Additionally, all respondents highly value customer reviews and say they are especially important when searching for product information. This can be explained by the fact that many participants said that reviews had an impact on their product choices. It is seen that participants attach importance to knowledge and experience in online customer analysis when searching for product information. Additionally, only a small percentage of respondents expressed doubts about the reliability of online consumers. According to TripAdvisor, the general attitude of the reviews is also positive. Participants rated this review as fair and trustworthy.

Secondly, "How does it affect online customers' perception?" the question is. it works. We examined two variables: age and gender. Age appears to affect time spent on social media; People aged 21-25 spend the most time on the internet. However, no differences were found in the customer perception analysis. The same goes for gender. Men and women in the research group did not show any significant difference in the customer perception analysis. For example, we see that they value reviews equally, viewing reviews as balanced and trustworthy, and equally valuing the people who write them. Looking closely at the reviews of four different reviews, it can be assumed that participants wanted a medium to long-term review. The correlation shows that length can also improve the overall fit of the analysis.

The real question that needs to be answered is: "Do profile reviews have an impact on the credibility of online customer reviews?" Reviews written by people with established profiles get the best responses in terms of credibility. In this case, the relationship indicates that the more trustworthy the reviewer appears, the more trustworthy the review as a whole appears to the reader. This relationship means that whenever a person's profile appears untrustworthy, the review as a whole becomes unreliable.

5.2 Limitations of present study

This study has several limitations. The first limitation is time. Since this research was conducted as part of a graduate course, the entire process, from writing the research paper to online research, only took about two months. If you have a lot of time, you can dig deeper and analyze different factors associated with online customer reviews, especially on TripAdvisor. Additionally, more time can increase the number of respondents and make the results more valid and important for the research.

Another limitation is that most of the participants in the research were students of the University of Twente. This is because the two researchers distributing the research paper are both students at the university and therefore the relationship between them is important here. Therefore, the results cannot be generalized as the study required a large number of participants in terms of profession and age.

The third limitation is research bias. Many aspects of the research are the responsibility of researchers, such as formulating questions and analyzing results. For example, when analyzing the survey results, some of the instructions to the participants were listed as short, medium and long.

5.3 Possible directions for future research

As social media grows rapidly and becomes more important to marketers and business enterprises, many different aspects of online customer reviews will be evaluated in the future. In the case of business travel, an interesting way would be to examine the words of the review and examine how these affect the credibility of the review. Word choice, use of slang, whether the text I present is legal or illegal, etc. It's worth a look. In addition, this

research should be conducted with more participants and different cultures. Age, gender, occupation, socioeconomic background, and other variables may be important when determining trust.

Additionally, differences in the discussion of the phone call can be compared if and why there is a difference in the customer's thoughts and comments. Additionally, it would be interesting to learn whether there are significant differences across industries. Although there are many factors that affect the reliability of reviews of travel products or technology products, for example. Additionally, the results of this research may change over time as recent developments in customer reviews may influence customer perceptions of online shopping. Many review sites have had problems with companies providing fake reviews. These can lead to decreased credibility of review sites and distrust among users. Finally, they harm the review sites and companies that receive these fake reviews.

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